

little as 10 mg. can be determined by this method. Common anions like chloride, bromide, nitrate, etc. do not interfere in the determination of the violet colour complexes [Y L Cu, Mg], [Y L Cu, Ca], [Y L Cu, Sr] and [Y L Cu, Ba] are still stable upto 250°, above this temperature they start decomposing. Only the MgCu complexes are soluble in methyl alcohol. The remaining are insoluble in water, acetone, alcohol, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, ether, benzene and pyridine.

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Spectrophotometric studies of Cu(II) complexes with Schiff Bases

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THE complexes of copper with sulphamethazine salicylaldimine (SUMTSA), sulphadiazinesalicylaldimine (SUDSA) and sulphamerazine salicylaldimine (SUMRSA) have been studied spectrophotometrically at 20°. Cu(II) forms 1:2 complexes with these ligands. Stability constants are determined by applying Job's method and Raghavrao's method. Free energy values have also been evaluated.

The synthesis and analysis of ligands have been described in previous communications^{1,2,3}.

A Beckman model Du spectrophotometer was used for absorption measurements. The studies were carried out in acetone/alcohol (1:1 by vol.) mixture.

The max. for copper acetate was found at 765nm., that of Cu-SUDSA complex at 330nm. (pH7.0) of Cu-SUMTSA complex at 395nm. (pH7.0) and of Cu-SUMRSA complex at 340nm (pH7.0). These wavelengths were chosen for the study of stoichiometry of the components by Job's method of continuous variation using equimolar solutions. The validity of Beer's law was seen. The absorbance measurements were carried out after 24 hr of equilibration. The colour did not fade even after a week. The pH of the solution were adjusted at required level by using different buffer solutions.

The stability constants were calculated from absorbance data (a) by extrapolation of Job's curve

obtained by using equimolar solutions as suggested by Raghavarao⁴, (b) using Job's method of nonequimolar solutions as modified by Foley-Anderson⁵ and Dey⁶.

The values of stability constants and free energy changes are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I. STABILITY CONSTANTS

S. No.	Complex	Method A		Method B	
		log K	$\frac{\Delta G}{K \text{ cal/mole}}$	log K	$\frac{\Delta G}{K \text{ cal/mole}}$
1	Cu-SUMTSA	9.08	-11.35	10.04	-12.55
2	Cu-SUDSA	9.65	-12.06	10.52	-13.15
3	Cu-SUMRSA	9.03	-11.29	10.40	-13.00

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The Effect of Bubble Formation on Hydrogen Overpotential at Mercury Cathodes

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BUBBLE overvoltages¹ were traditionally recorded to indicate the "minimum" overvoltage for electrolytic gas evolution reactions. Contemporary electrode kinetics² pays no heed to such subjective observations, which appear to have no fundamental significance. We wish to report a new effect, that of bubble formation on hydrogen overpotential measurements at high purity (5X distilled) mercury.

A centro-symmetric cell was used, with connecting tubes to the anode and reference hydrogen electrodes directly above the mercury cup. Hydrochloric acid

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